

Automatic Light Intensity Control System

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Abstract

This paper demonstrates an easy and energy efficient automatic light intensity control system which does not need much maintenance. The cost of the system is 125 rupees(Rs.). Earlier the high intensity incandescent bulbs were used. The disadvantage of these high intensity incandescent bulbs is that the intensity cannot be varied according to the requirement. To overcome this limitation "Automatic Light Intensity Control System" is developed.

To overcome the limitations specified above, it makes use of LDR(Light Dependent Resistor) whose resistance varies according to the brightness of the surrounding environment and simultaneously its intensity can be varied and controlled automatically. The system also comprises of a TRIAC, DIAC, Capacitor, Resistor and connecting wires. So when external light is low, the light intensity is high and as external light increases the intensity of Incandescent Bulbs decreases accordingly to save power.

In this the sensor which will be used is LDR(Light Dependent Resistor).The resistance of the LDR (Light Dependent Resistor) varies according to the brightness in the surrounding environment .It decreases when its dark outside and increases when its bright outside or it varies inversely with respect to the brightness of the surrounding environment or the light falling on its surface.

By using the LDR we can control the intensity of the incandescent bulbs. The resistance of the LDR varies according to the brightness in the surrounding environment. Triac had been used here to control the current through the circuit. Diac had been here to trigger the Triac(gate triggering) a protective resistance had also been used here.

Keywords: Triac, Diac, LDR and Capacitor.

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INTRODUCTION

The main consideration in the field of technology are Automation, Power consumption and cost effectiveness. Automation is intended to reduce man power with the help of intelligent systems, Power saving is the main consideration forever as the source of the power(Thermal, Hydro etc.,) are getting diminished due to various reasons.

The main objective is to save electrical energy automatically by the application of LDR(Light Dependent Resistor).We want to save power automatically instead of doing manual, Manual

control is prone to errors and leads to energy wastages.

By using the LDR (Light Dependent Resistor) we can control the intensity of the Incandescent bulbs. The resistance of the LDR (Light Dependent Resistor) changes as per the brightness of the surrounding environment, the resistance decreases in the darkness and increases in brightness i.e. resistance of the LDR is inversely proportional to the light falling on the surface of the LDR so when it is dark outside the bulb will glow brightly and when it is bright outside the bulb will turn off or it will glow dim as per the brightness outside and thus the

brightness of the Incandescent Bulb varies and controlled as per the brightness of the surrounding environment automatically. Hence this will result in power saving or more precisely energy conservation.

The idea do not consume huge amount of electricity and illuminate area with the highest intensity of light whenever required. Inefficient lighting wastes significant financial resources every year. Use of Energy efficient technologies can reduce cost of the lighting drastically and eventually will help in the conservation of energy resources.

The term TRIAC stands for Triode for Alternating Current. A TRIAC is a semiconductor device with three terminals that control the flow of current, thus the name TRIAC. Unlike SCR, TRIAC is bidirectional while SCR is unidirectional. It is ideal for operation utilizing AC power for switching purposes since it can control current flow for both halves in an alternating current cycle.[1]

The operation of the TRIAC is based on the thyristor. It facilitates the switching function in AC electrical components and systems. They are widely used in light dimmers as in this case because they allow both halves of the AC cycle to be utilized. As a result, this makes them more efficient in power usage.[1]

DIAC stands for "Diode for Alternating Current". A DIAC is a device which has two electrodes, and It is a device which consists of four layers and two terminals unlike the Triac which consists of three terminals. The gate terminal is not present in DIAC. It is a member of the thyristor family. DIACs are used in the triggering of Triac[2].

In this case it had been used here to change the firing angle of the Triac.

A photo resistor or light dependent resistor is component that is sensitive to light. It works on the principle of photoconductivity. As light falls on the semiconductor some of the energy is transferred to the electrons.[3]

This gives some of them sufficient energy to break free from the crystal lattice so that they can then conduct electricity. This results in a lowering of the resistance of the semiconductor and hence the overall LDR (Light Dependent Resistor) resistance. The process is fast and as more light shines on the LDR semiconductor, so more electrons are released to conduct electricity and the resistance falls further.[3]

A Capacitor is a passive component that has the ability to store the energy in the form of potential difference between its plates. [4]

In this the capacitor along with a fixed resistor and LDR i.e. a potential divider circuit determines the time constant and gate terminal of TRIAC is triggered with the help of DIAC. Here a protective resistance of 100k Ω had also been used.

II. WORKING

The working of this project is quite simple. The resistance of the LDR varies according to the brightness of the surrounding environment. As a result the voltage output of the potential divider circuit also varies.

DIAC had been used here to trigger the TRIAC (by Gate triggering). A protective resistance of 100K Ω had been used here as well. The capacitor in series with the potentiometer helps to trigger the TRIAC by changing the firing angle..

TRIAC had been used here to control the current through the circuit. Now whenever the brightness of the surrounding environment varies the resistance of the LDR (Light Dependent Resistor) also varies. Whenever it is bright outside the resistance increases and when it is dark outside the resistance is reduced.

The intensity of the incandescent bulb thus varies accordingly.

III.CONCLUSION

This system is of high utility. The system can also be installed in the houses as well to reduce the wastage of electricity and other places such as schools etc. The system can be installed in urban as well as the rural areas. The main advantage is not only that the energy is being conserved but also that no manual system is required to operate it. Also the system is very economical.

The system has been given in the Figure 1 given below.

Figure 1

IV.LIMITATIONS

This system had a limitation that the intensity of only the incandescent bulb can be controlled. The intensity of LED bulbs cannot be controlled using this system.

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